

EARTH SCIENCES

FUNDAMENTALS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELECTRONIC MAPS AND MAPS OF ENVIRONMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF SOILS ON THE BASIS OF GIS

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ABSTRACT

Large- and medium-scale soil mapping finds its application in various fields, including in solving problems of soil-ecological and agricultural monitoring. The use of modern computer, geo-information and Internet technologies provides new tools for the accumulation and processing of soil data, and also opens up the possibility of connecting to the analysis of other natural and geographical factors. Comprehensive analysis of multi-time, multi-scale and heterogeneous natural-soil information allows one to obtain not only a more objective assessment of soil formation processes, but also numerical characteristics of the soil and soil cover, which are necessary for practical use. The development of methods for converting archived soil materials into digital format, the formation of attribute data structures that provide a unified cartographic space of the region are fundamental steps in creating a soil map of a regional level.

Keywords: geographic information systems, interactive map, electronic soil map, ecological soil assessment.

INTRODUCTION

In developing countries, special attention is paid to the agricultural sector, which is the main condition for social sustainability. As one of the main directions of economic policy in our republic, favorable conditions have been created for the development of this sphere.

A number of questions have been raised in the state programs being implemented by scientists and specialists working in the agricultural sector. Preparation of an electronic soil map of Azerbaijan; soil inventory; land cadastre; land management, economic assessment, salinization, study of the degree of erosion and their mapping, creation of crop rotation systems, restoration issues, reconstruction of the amelioration and irrigation system, electronic agriculture and selection of zoned highly productive seeds are important tasks facing specialists.

At the present time, the creation of interactive electronic soil maps and maps of environmental assessment of soils is in the way of solving higher problems. In GIS studies, the availability of information on layers significantly improves the quality of terrain maps, which include terrain relief, soil-forming rocks, vegetation cover, forest structure, and other features. Unlike paper, electronic maps provide an opportunity to analyze, modify and reclassify data. From this point of view, it is important to create a system of information about space and geographic information, in general, for optimal land management in the territory. To implement such a database, you can use software on modern geographic information systems. In this regard, the authors for the first time created an electronic map platform covering the entire territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan based on GIS software, which supports an interactive update mode.

This map covers the entire scale of the spectrum and meets the requirements of e-agriculture and other public information systems, which are based on the use of data space. For conducting soil, agrochemical and interdisciplinary research on the platform, a method of

plastic relief was developed. Also prepared a detailed methodology for the compilation of digital soil and environmentally assessment maps of soils using 3D visualization.

The map is an Arabic word. This is a reduced, generalized image of the Earth's surface, another celestial body or extraterrestrial space constructed in a cartographic projection, showing objects or phenomena located on it in a certain system of conventional signs. Geographic map - a depiction of a model of the Earth's surface in a reduced form, containing a coordinate grid with conventional symbols on the plane.

The electronic map is a cartographic image generated on the basis of digital map data and visualized on a computer video monitor or a video screen of other devices (for example, satellite navigator). The electronic map is based on data from digital maps and GIS databases.

Digital map - a digital terrain model created by digitizing cartographic sources, photogrammetric processing of remote sensing data, digital recording.

An interactive map is an electronic map that operates in a two-way interactive mode between the user and the computer, and is a visual information system.

As you know, the easiest way to explore the landscape is to compile its digital model. Before the discovery of GIS, the creation of such models was often impossible.

It should be noted that in 2011, on behalf of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, the State Impact Committee on Land and Cartography for the first time compiled an interactive electronic map of Azerbaijan mainly for socially oriented purposes. Scientific approaches that meet modern requirements in the past have led to the emergence of a fundamentally scientific approach to the compilation of interactive electronic soil maps and environmental assessment of soils in Azerbaijan.

The marking of the contours of the earth reflects the reality in addition to the height of the relief, determines the indicators of latitude and longitude on the plane, as well as modern digital models (3D), aerial photographs and satellite images, and software. This required the preparation of new terrain maps based on GIS technology.

STAGES OF PREPARATION OF ORTHOPHOTOMAPS FROM AERIAL AND SPACE IMAGES

The creation of airborne materials consists of the following steps:

1. Preparatory work. At this stage, planning of optimal flight routes, division of the territory into blocks, measurements of the location control point by blocks are carried out. The area for filming is divided into 4-5 route blocks. It helps to make work faster. The location of control points within the block is determined. Flight routes are determined by the camera's own camera software, which will be filmed for flight management. Depending on the weather forecast for 1-2 days before departure, the control points of the Earth are measured. These points are very important for determining the coordinates in the images and determining their position on the ground.

Figure 1

2. Flying. External orientation parameters of captured images (center coordinates, flight altitude, omega, kappa rotation angles) are deleted. At the end of the flight, data is processed in accordance with the

actual colors of the earth's surface. Depending on the number of images, this process takes several days. The coordinates of the images are customized to fit any coordinate system and projection (figure 2).

Figure 2

3. Information for accommodation. The orthobase project, which includes the coordinate system and parameters of the output product, is installed in the software (figure 3). The program includes the parameters

of the external orientation and the results of measurements of land control points. As part of the software built project. Figures that are not associated with any coordinates, using other parameters are transferred to the original location and fixed.

Figure 3

4. Aerial triangulation in progress. Images are interconnected, given in coordinates and errors are balanced. On the basis of captured images, stereo models are created (two images create a stereo image), they are edited, and a terrain model is created. Images are trans-

verse and longitudinally covered. Images are automatically merged by common points. Based on the control points of the location and coordinates of the center of the images included in the block are closed on the plane (figure 4).

Figure 4

5. Results are analyzed. The parameters of the output product are entered into the orthophoto-plan based on the model of the digital domain. Then the mosaic

process is conducted. To get more accurate orthophotoplans, a digital model of the area is added below the coordinate image of the plane (figure 5).

Figure 5

6. Mosaic orthophotoplans are cut to any part of the project (figure 6).

Figure 6

Phases of orthophoto preparation from space images (in Erdas Imagine) consist of the following stages:

1. Counting the pyramid of the captured image. The space image is “presented” to the software, and the process of obtaining optimal true colors begins (figure 7).

Figure 7

2. Measurement of coordinate and altitude indicators in the field, where the exact contour of the area is determined. The exact contours in the image (horizontal lines, buildings, angles of calculations) are

determined, and their coordinates and heights are measured in the area. This information is used to determine the coordinates of the image. That is, the position of uncoordinated images on the ground is determined (figure 8).

Figure 8

3. A project is created in the software and image parameters are entered. The created project includes the coordinate system of the inserted image, projection,

color gamut (brightness, true color correlation) and recognition accuracy (figure 9).

Figure 9

4. The points are added to the image, and the root-mean-square error is minimized. Certain coordinates and heights are included in the project. For maximum detail, the locations of these points are viewed on a larger scale, and the point on the pixels are aligned. To do this, consider images taken when shooting the coordinates of this point. Photo helps to determine the exact

contour of the image. After the software calculates the error of the mean square. This error can be minimized after the rectification of the space image and the inclusion of a digital model of the region in the project. There is a resolution limit of image accuracy (the area in which the pixel is located). This indicator, when it is below the limit, ends (figure 10).

Figure 10

5. A DEM file is selected, geometric and graphic parameters are determined for the file that will be the mosaic and the mosaic process begins. Includes product parameters (projection, color gamut, distinctive accu-

racy). Marked model of the digital domain. This information determines the characteristics of the finished product. Thus, the process of building different space images begins (figure 11).

Figure 11

6. Then the mosaic file is truncated at a specific index. Images embedded in each other are called mosaic files. Since the combined images are complex,

the ready-to-use orthorectification product is cropped in accordance with the nomenclature divided by the area, that is, any territorial division (figure 12).

Figure 12

PRINCIPLES OF SOIL MAPPING BASED ON AERO AND SPACE MATERIALS

Modern mapping of space objects, including land cover, landscape complexes and other objects and phenomena observed in nature, requires three main elements: 1) an exact geographical basis (topographic maps of different sizes); 2) aerospace photography; 3) GIS software for electronic mapping.

As is known, the exact geographical basis (topographic map at the required scale) is the geographical basis of maps of various subjects, including maps of the area. Paper maps of topographic maps have been used for many years to prepare soil maps. Over the past decade, much attention has been paid to the preparation of multidimensional topographic maps using aerospace materials along with surface studies. However, practice shows that topographic maps, as a rule, are subject to generalization both in paper and electronic versions, and it is not enough to have a clear topographic basis for preparing maps that accurately reflect reality. It is also important to use periodic renewable aviation and space materials in separate blocks.

Our republic does not have sufficient experience in the preparation of maps, especially maps of the terrain, aerial photography, space photographic materials and compatible computer programs. This can be explained by several reasons: 1) lack of access to aerospace materials for most specialists (the presence of legal and administrative gaps in this area); 2) lack of skills required by a number of specialists in the use of aero and space materials and computer programs (ArcGIS). Nevertheless, one cannot deny the role of soil and other maps displayed by traditional methods in the development of various fields of science and in managing the country's economy.

Many of the information relating to geographical elements (hydrography, road networks, homes, borders, etc.), described in the State Soil Map of Azerbaijan (1: 100,000), which is compiled in the traditional way, reflect the current state of the 80s of the last century. In addition, the contours of the soil do not reflect reality. For this reason, it is important to use aerial photographs and satellite images that reflect the current state of the Earth when designing modern terrain maps.

Fragment of a traditional soil map

Fragment of a soil map created on the basis of orthophoto

Figure 13

As can be seen from the illustration, the actual state of the space provided by the aerobatics allows for a more accurate representation of the four contours of the earth - meadow-marsh salt marshes (92), marsh meadow-meadow (94), tyr-like salt marshes (99) and scaly saline (100) (figure 13).

INSTRUCTIONS FOR LARGE-SCALE RESEARCH AND MAPPING OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

Large-scale soil and geobotanical studies based on the "Laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the State Land Cadastre, Monitoring Soils and Land Use" (1998) are carried out once every ten years; agrochemical studies once every five years in soils prone to erosion, salinization and degradation. Soil studies are carried out in three stages: preparation for research, field research and desk research. At the preparatory stage, the following works are carried out: the name of the area where the object of research is located, the forms of ownership of land, land users and the area of their use, geographical location, scale of research, etc. are determined.

In the preparation stage, in order to use and create in-kind soil maps of the object under study, topographic materials, aerial photographs and space photographs, or a photographic plan, a map and a land management plan are collected. These materials, complementing each other are used in soil mapping in the field. When using these materials, the transfer of soil contours in nature are carried out on the basis of aerial photographs. Topographic maps are used to collect data on the relief of the study area, slope slopes and absolute altitude. The revised land management plan is used to obtain accurate information about the farmer sites in the study area. In the case of the lack of modern orthophoto materials, you can use the Internet programs GoogleEarth and GoogleMap.

Photographs, topographic maps, and corrections based on the scale of the geographic location plan must meet or exceed the scale of the survey. In the absence of a large-scale topographic map, an aerial photograph plan is used. Small-scale topographic maps are used in the general direction of the aerial route plan and when transmitting altitude. If the scale of the survey is 1:5000, it is desirable to use an aerial photograph plan from 1:5000 to 1:10,000, and from 1:10,000 to 1:25,000, then the scale is 1:25,000.

The cartographic group develops the original electronic version of the map of river basins, land cadastral areas, soils transferred to municipal property, summer and winter pastures, farm agricultural lands and land plots for permanent use by private owners, based on topographic maps, photo plans and revised land management plans. In the original version, conventional signs should be transferred from the topographic map and from the photomap, so that land can be placed on the soil map.

The following indicators should be indicated in the original soil map: boundaries of landowners and users; farm boundaries and their symbols; forest belts, hydrographic networks (rivers, irrigated and ameliorative networks); settlements and public buildings; roads (rail and road). The original is made

and the name of the card is written. In the clean edges of the map, tables are given that reflect the explanations to the map (legend, conventional signs, neighboring lands, authors and a stamp).

One of the important issues at the preparation stage is to determine the degree of dismemberment (categories) that need to be studied before conducting a study. The number of cuts intended for research is determined by the scale of the study and the dissection of the soil cover. Under the dismemberment refers to the frequency of changes in the boundaries of land units in nature and color (mosaic) caused by certain factors in the soil cover. In this case, the boundaries of the contours of the soil increase and become more complex. Thus, the following levels of dissection are determined taking into account the economic and natural factors that make up the complexity of the soil cover.

Category I - consists of plains and a dry steppe semi-desert climate. The complexity of the soil cover up to 10%.

Category II - this refers to the hilly foothills, plains and dry steppe semi-desert climate, as well as areas with the same soil cover. In the soil cover, this category includes areas with fluctuations of 10-20% of the complexity of various relief elements.

Category III - lowlands with semi-desert areas with dry subtropical climatic conditions: a) it takes into account the complexity (mosaic), which is created by the influence of soil-forming rocks that form on the soil cover; b) this refers to the dry steppe zone, irrigated areas, as well as areas where the soil-forming rocks are identical. Complexity up to 20%.

Category IV - provides for soils of areas with low and medium mountainous relief conditions of mountain steppes: a) the complex of the created impact of the relief and soil formation of rocks is 20-40%; b) the density of the valleys, the complexity due to the slopes and the steepness of the slopes is up to 50%; c) complexity associated with growing in calm relief elements is up to 15%; d) river bays, mountain plateau, arrays with dry bushes; e) subalpine and alpine meadows, etc.

Category V - lands of regions with more than 50% of the complex and fragmented in the soil cover with the relief of certain elements: a) land reclaimed in the Aran zone, irrigated areas prone to re-salinization; b) semi-desert dry steppe zones fragmented by valleys and arrays complicated by different soil-forming rocks; c) arrays with a complexity of more than 50%, with signs of salinization.

The main tasks facing field research are as follows: compiling a soil map reflecting the complexity of soil distribution in nature; collection of data allowing owners to identify soil properties for efficient use of soil cover.

The most important document in soil research is a soil map, compiled on the basis of available data, which should be specifically considered. A large-scale soil map must be very accurate, because the more accurate the maps, the more effective from an agronomic point of view. Accuracy of the soil map means the degree of compliance for the terrain on which the soil units are

located in the plan. Any incorrect display of map accuracy may occur during use.

The magnitude of errors in the placement of soil contours depends on the severity of soil boundaries in nature. The sharp distance of the borders should not exceed ± 0.5 mm in the aerial photograph, and not more than ± 2 mm on the top layer of the topographic map. A clear choice of boundaries is usually best illustrated

on the materials of aerial photographs and in horizontal form in topographic maps. In this case, the magnitude of the bias error in the aerial photograph should not exceed ± 2 mm, and in the topomap it should not exceed ± 4 mm. When the boundaries are not clearly selected, the magnitude of the displacement error units can be up to ± 10 mm when working with any material (table 1).

Table 1.

The magnitude of the errors of soil boundaries when placed on the map

The degree of clarity of the boundaries of soil units in nature	Errors in scale (mm on the map, m in kind)		Example for soil boundaries
	1:5000	1:10000	
Clearly defined borders	$\pm 1,0-4,0$ 5-20	$\pm 0,5-2,0$ 5-20	1. Meadow-marsh and meadow-gray soils 2. Mountain brown forest and mountain steppe brown soils 3. Floodplain meadow forest soils
Clearly defined borders	$\pm 4,0-8,0$ 20-40	$\pm 2,0-4,0$ 20-40	1. Gray-brown and meadow gray-brown soils 2. Solonchak and saline solonets soils 3. Mountain meadow and mountain forest soils
Gradually marked boundaries	$\pm 10-20,0$ 50-100	$\pm 10,0$ 100	1. Normal gray-brown and gray-brown soils 2. Pseudo-podzol yellow and podzol yellow-gley soils

The minimum area of soil circles reflected on the soil map depends on the visibility of the boundaries and the magnitude of the scale. The movement of the minimum circle in kind to the cards is governed by the magnitude of the scale. From this point of view, it is

desirable to measure the minimum limit of soil units in the area where the boundaries are sharply visible 25 mm², clearly selected 50 mm² and gradually selected 400 mm² (table 2).

Table 2.

Minimum measurement of land boundaries on the map

The degree of clarity of the boundaries of soil units in nature	Minimum measurement of land boundaries in soil maps (mm ² on the map, ha in nature)		
	Scale		
	1: 5000	1:10000	1: 25000
Sharp border	$\frac{25}{0,06}$	$\frac{25}{0,25}$	$\frac{25}{1,5}$
Clear border	$\frac{50}{0,25}$	$\frac{50}{0,5}$	$\frac{50}{3,0}$
Gradual boundary	$\frac{400}{1,0}$	$\frac{400}{4,0}$	$\frac{400}{25,0}$

When describing the size of the minimum soil circles in terms of the plan, complexity, flaws or mosaic observed in the soil cover are ignored. When it comes to spotting, the contours of the soil are counted on several meters and even tens of millions of m³ as a result of certain natural and anthropogenic factors. They are commonly called genetically related soils.

In the soil cover, small spots replace each other (5-30 m), which means the complexity of the microrelief. This is also seen in a number of interrelated types or subtypes. The degree of complexity or spotting of the soil cover is expressed as a percentage. In areas where any type of soil or subtype is common, there are spots that differ sharply from the characteristics of the semi-type, they are grouped into a soil map and are combined

into complex soils. In this case, the name of the contour complex is given in accordance with the preferred component. In order to correctly describe the complexity of the map, the following gradations are conditionally accepted: 10-20%, 20-30% and 30-50%.

Planned and reasonable contours on the map, depending on their size, should be characterized by full and half cuts. If several small contours are repeated in an array, then they can be characterized by half-cuts. If small contours cause spotting or complexity in the soil cover, then the factors that create complexity should be justified by cuts.

During soil field studies, each baseline and test half-section should be coordinated based on GPS (Global Positioning System). Depending on the size

and degree of complexity of the headquarters, each section of the section or half-section is indicated by a hectare (table 3).

Table 3.

The area is 1 soil section, ha

Scope of research	Area 1 cut, ha					Area on the map, cm ²				
	Degree of difficulty									
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5
1: 2000	5	3	2	1,5	1	250	75	50	37	25
1: 5000	10	8	6	5	4	40	32	24	20	16
1: 10000	25	20	18	15	10	25	20	18	15	10
1: 25000	80	65	50	40	25	12,8	10,4	8,0	6,4	4,0
1: 50000	150	130	110	80	50	6,0	5,2	4,4	3,2	2,0

The quantitative norm of cross-sections per unit area, shown in the table, is an estimate, and their number may vary depending on the scale, as well as the amount of soil cover. The ratio of bases, checks and half-cuts is determined as follows. If the study is conducted on the basis of a topographic map of 1:4:5, and if on the basis of a photo plan - 1:4:2.

The main cuts are made for a thorough study of the soil and subsoil layers. Therefore, when laying the main cuts, the soil layer is completely, and the top layer of soil-forming rocks must be open. Their depth should reach 1,5-2,0 m with the intervention of groundwater and solid rock. If the groundwater is in depth (4 m), in this case there are several deep cuts in typical soils. All genetic layers of the soil layer should be open, and when checking the cuts, the transition of the soil layer to the soil-forming rocks should be established. Depending on the soil-climatic zones and the thickness of the soil layer, the depth of the section should be from 0,75 to 1,5 m. It is desirable that the depth in the Aran plain be from 0,50-0,75 m, and in the mountainous and foothill zones, 0,25-0,50 m.

Before the study by a soil scientist, images of aerial photographs of soil sections are taken, or transferred to a topographic map. Cuts with high accuracy facilitate the use of these materials during field studies when transferring to a map. The accuracy of the placement of cuts on aerial photographs and topographic maps should be $\pm 0,3 \pm 3,0$ mm. Some soil features can be established in the field, such as carbonate (with 10% HCl-acid), iron oxide and acidification. Painting the genetic layers in the field journal during the cutting of cuts, helps to easily establish morphological and genetic properties of the soil in the office. After the description of the section, samples of soil weighing 0.5 kg are taken by genetic layers. In the soils of the mountain and foothill zones, to determine the thickness of the soil layer, skeletal, podzolic, gley, etc. soil samples are taken for laboratory tests.

During studies of alpine soils subject to erosion, the extent to which the topsoil was washed away should

be seriously considered. If the battery humus layer of soil was washed away, and an illuvial layer (2nd layer) appeared, in field conditions on the map it is necessary to note the degree of washing (weak, medium, strong, very strong).

Operations on large-scale soil analyzes are divided into two groups: analysis of soil samples by common or genetic horizons; agrochemical analyzes. On the basis of analytical data (for example, absorbed sodium, absorptivity, permeability, acidity, carbonate, etc.) important cartograms are made (acidity, alkalinity, carbonate, alkalinity, salinity, etc.).

The final map should display the following information:

a) basic map information: soil boundaries of owners; boundaries and contours of farms; forest belts; hydrographic chain; residential items (showing common boundaries); road chains (railways, highways, unpaved); surface rock networks, valleys and beams.

b) basic soil information: soil contours, their signs and intra-contour indices; soil size distribution; salinity and alkalinity; soil-forming rocks; irrigation (irrigated).

MAPPING OF SOILS OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN ON THE BASIS OF GIS

Soil maps based on geographic information systems are compiled mainly in the following sequence: 1. Vectorization: borders of the state, administrative district and municipality, settlements, hydrographic objects, relief, boundaries of soil contours, etc. (figure 14). 2. Collecting a database of vectorized layers (various information about layers). For example, information on quality indicators: physical and chemical properties of soils (humus, total nitrogen, phosphorus, total absorbed bases, pH, particle size distribution, etc.), soil salinization, alkalinity, erosion, etc. 3. Inclusion of attribute information by layers in the database and the creation of an interactive map (figure 15a and 15b). 4. Retrieving information from a database online (figure 16). 5. Soil-cartographic works (figure 17).

Figure 14

Figure 15a

Figure 15b

Figure 16

Figure 17

6. 3D image based on digital height model (figure 18, 19).

Figure 18. Azerbaijan's height model

Figure 19. Digital height model based on 3D model

DEVELOPMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELECTRONIC MAPS OF ECOLOGICAL SOIL ASSESSMENT BASED ON GIS

Scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of the ecological assessment of soils began to develop in our republic in the early 1990s. The historical necessity of this scientific direction depends on several reasons. In the 1950s and 1960s, the development of two independent scientific studies in the field of soil science - the theory of soil ecology and comparative assessment of soil, i.e., soil assessment, was linked. Although both scientific trends developed in parallel over the years, at the turn of the 1980s and early 90s of the twentieth century there was a favorable scientific, theoretical and methodological basis for the formation of the concept of "environmental assessment of soil". Another important reason is the appearance in the world, as well as in our country, environmental problems associated with the soil, as in all biospheric components.

In the 1980s and 1990s, a number of researchers used the relief plastic technique to create maps on various topics. However, these studies were episodic, and were conducted in small territories in different regions of Azerbaijan. The first large-scale study in this area was carried out in 1985 according to the map of the relief of the Republic of Azerbaijan at a scale of 1:200,000. This material was used in the compilation of soil maps in 1991, and environmental assessment maps of Azerbaijan's soils in 2003.

The second important element of the environmental assessment of soils is the development of a system of special assessment scales for the degree of individual soil characteristics. In the course of the first studies (in the early 90s) G.Sh. Mammadov made these scales a

generalized form for the soils of the republic. In many cases, these scales consisted of a system of theoretical views on the properties and characteristics of the soil. Thus, the variability of any soil parameter was estimated using generalized expressions ("good", "medium", "high", etc.). According to the academician, the ecological assessment of the soil is based on the principle of expressing these relationships in quantitative terms, in contrast to the soil ecology, which has theoretical knowledge about the interaction and effects between the soil and the environment. At the same time, the ecological assessment of the soil was carried out using ecological scales characterizing each of the various environmental parameters.

On the other hand, the ecological scale of the soil characterizes the state of its formation and the advantages of the soil cover for one purpose or another. For the compilation of such scales, it is important that there is information on the relief, soil-forming rocks, hydrological conditions, soil and plant studies, climatic conditions, etc. The developed ecological scales allow us to present the conditions of life on earth as a single system. At this stage, two goals are achieved: a comparative description of the soil-forming state and the determination of the ecological state of the soil.

A new concept was adopted by adopting the general scheme of the methodology presented by S.Z.Mammadova (2006) and G.Sh.Mammadov (1998). S.Z.Mammadova suggested that the concept of an environmental assessment of soils is not a concept of soil-ecological indicators of land ("good", "average", "high", etc.), but the idea of finding the final score with

using specific figures, and made a map of the environmental assessment of the soils of the Lankaran region on a scale of 1:100.000.

CONCLUSION

Thus, at the final stage, interactive electronic maps of environmental assessment of soils are compiled on the basis of GIS, taking into account land and environmental factors.

A map of the ecological assessment of soils compiled taking into account the relief of plastics (G.Sh.Mammadov, 2003)

Interactive electronic map of ecological soil assessment based on GIS

№	Topraq	H	Y	T	BIP	Md	Humus	pH	w.a.	grading	salinization	erosion	B	points	economic places	etc.
1	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
2	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
3	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
4	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
5	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
6	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
7	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
8	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
9	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
10	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
11	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
12	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
13	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
14	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
15	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
16	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
17	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
18	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
19	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
20	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
21	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
22	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
23	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
24	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
25	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
26	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
27	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
28	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
29	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
30	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
31	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
32	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
33	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
34	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
35	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
36	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
37	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
38	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
39	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
40	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
41	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
42	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
43	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
44	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
45	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
46	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
47	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
48	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
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50	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
51	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
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59	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
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61	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
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77	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
78	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
79	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
80	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
81	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
82	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
83	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
84	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80	0.80										
85	Dağ çarxarı	2000	1200-1400	1000-2000	11.80											

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